

Incremental vs. Disruptive Innovation Strategies: Comparative Effects on Organizational Performance in the Textile Industrial Sector

Stratégies d'innovations Incrémentales vs. Disruptives : Effets croisés sur la Performance organisationnelle dans le secteur industriel textile

LAKHLIFI Fatima Zahrae

Doctorante-monitrice en Sciences économiques et gestion

Université Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdellah

Laboratoire Interdisciplinaire de Recherche en Economie, Finance et Management des Organisations (LIREFIMO)

Fès-Maroc

ABDELLAOUI Mohammed

Enseignant-chercheur en Sciences économiques et gestion

Université Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdellah

Laboratoire Interdisciplinaire de Recherche en Economie, Finance et Management des Organisations (LIREFIMO)

Fès-Maroc

Date de soumission : 12/10/2024

Date d'acceptation : 25/11/2024

Pour citer cet article :

LAKHLIFI, F. & ABDELLAOUI, M. (2024) «Incremental vs. Disruptive Innovation Strategies: Comparative Effects on Organizational Performance in the Textile Industrial Sector», Revue Internationale du chercheur «Volume 5 : Numéro 4» pp : 882-902

Résumé

Cet article examine les effets comparés des innovations incrémentales et disruptives sur la performance organisationnelle dans le secteur industriel textile, en s'inscrivant dans le cadre de la politique industrielle marocaine 2023-2030, qui privilégie l'innovation comme levier de compétitivité. Une approche quantitative basée sur l'analyse de corrélations segmentées a été utilisée pour évaluer l'impact de chaque type d'innovation sur la productivité, la réduction des coûts, la qualité et la flexibilité, en tenant compte de la taille des entreprises, dans la région de Casablanca-Settat. L'étude s'appuie sur un échantillon de 174 entreprises, représentant différentes tailles et secteurs du textile industriel. Les résultats montrent que la taille de l'entreprise a une influence décisive sur le choix et l'impact des innovations adoptées, ainsi que sur le critère de performance. L'étude met en évidence l'importance d'adapter les stratégies d'innovation en fonction de la taille de l'entreprise pour maximiser les bénéfices, et ouvre des perspectives sur l'analyse des effets à long terme de ces innovations et leur application dans d'autres secteurs industriels.

Mots clés : Innovation ; Industrie ; Textile ; Maroc ; Comparaison

Abstract

This article examines the comparative effects of incremental and disruptive innovations on organizational performance in the textile industrial sector, within the framework of Morocco's industrial policy 2023-2030, which prioritizes innovation as a factor of competitiveness. A quantitative approach based on segmented correlation analysis was used to assess the impact of each type of innovation on productivity, cost reduction, quality and flexibility, taking into account company size, in the Casablanca-Settat region. The study is based on a sample of 174 companies, representing different sizes and sectors of the textile industry. The results show that company size has a decisive influence on the choice and impact of innovations adopted, as well as the performance criterion. The study highlights the importance of adapting innovation strategies according to company size in order to maximize profits, and opens up prospects for analyzing the long-term effects of these innovations and their application in other industrial sectors.

Keywords : Innovation; Industry; Textile; Morocco; Comparison

INTRODUCTION

As part of Morocco's industrial policy 2023-2030, the Moroccan government aims to strengthen the competitiveness and resilience of the industrial sector, with a particular focus on innovation as a key lever for growth (Ministère de l'Industrie et du Commerce, 2024). This strategic plan is based on several axes, including innovation, which is seen as an essential driver to support Moroccan companies in the face of global competition, and to boost their productivity, flexibility, and competitiveness. This focus on innovation is aligned with a broader vision of industrial modernization, aimed at transforming Morocco into a high-performance, sustainable industrial hub (Lakhlifi & Abdellaoui, 2024).

Numerous studies have explored the impact of innovation on business performance, highlighting positive effects on various performance indicators such as productivity, cost reduction, and improved product quality. However, few studies have focused specifically on the two main types of innovation: incremental innovation, which results in incremental improvements to existing processes and products, and disruptive innovation, which brings about radical changes by redefining methods or business models. This gap in the literature leaves a fundamental question unanswered: **Which is the most effective innovation between disruptive and incremental innovations for improving the performance of industrial companies?** To address this issue, a quantitative methodology was adopted, based on the analysis of segmented correlations between types of innovation (incremental and disruptive) and various performance indicators. Data were collected using a questionnaire administered to a sample of 174 industrial companies operating in the textile sector in the Casablanca-Settat region. This article begins with a literature review to establish the theoretical and conceptual foundations of the study. It then explores the concepts of incremental and disruptive innovation, before presenting the methodology adopted, including the study field, sample selection and analysis tools. Analysis of the results follows, examining the effects of innovations according to company size. The article concludes with a discussion of the implications of the results and prospects for future research.

By choosing this specific methodology and context, our study aims to provide empirical results that will enable us to better understand the dynamics of innovation within Moroccan industrial companies, and effectively guide strategic choices in terms of innovation.

1. LITERATURE REVIEW

1.1. Innovation and performance: A subjective notion?

Innovation is often perceived as a subjective notion, traversing a vast field of divergences and varied perspectives according to disciplines and industrial contexts. To take a closer look, Schilling (2005), an influential author in the field of innovation management, defines innovation as “the application of new ideas to generate value for an organization, whether this involves improving products, services or internal processes”. This definition highlights the pragmatic aspects of innovation: it is not limited to the mere generation of ideas, but includes their transformation into concrete, beneficial results (Glaeser & Land, 2024). It also reinforces the idea that innovation must add value, whether economic, social or operational, in line with the organization's objectives. This subjectivity around innovation underlines why it is often perceived differently by different sectors and companies (Oudda & Jallal, 2024).

Recent research has highlighted the complexity and subjectivity of the notion of innovation, showing that it takes a variety of forms and fulfills a variety of roles depending on organizational contexts and strategic objectives. Innovation is not simply reduced to the introduction of new technologies, artificial intelligence (Bahoo et al. 2023), or disruptive processes but also includes organizational and managerial adaptations designed to respond to external pressures or to anticipate future developments (Gama & Magistretti, 2023). In a study by Dupuis and Masingue (2023), innovation is seen as a tool for resilience. This organizational innovation aims to strengthen the ability of local entities to collaborate while responding to socio-economic needs and navigating between adaptive and anticipatory strategies. Similarly, the article by Rhazzane, Ahachmi, and Lahfidi (2023) examines innovation in the context of Moroccan cooperatives, where it is closely linked to business intelligence to enhance organizational resilience. Here, innovation is not only a means of introducing new products or processes but also a survival mechanism in an unstable and competitive environment (Azmat & al. 2024). Moreover, The study on governance in Moroccan SMEs adds a further dimension by positioning corporate governance as a lever for innovation (Aharouay & al. 2023). Governance plays a fundamental role in facilitating or hindering organizational innovation, depending on the power relations between shareholders, managers and other stakeholders. This shows another facet of the subjectivity of innovation: it becomes a tool for transformation through an appropriate governance structure, which balances the relationships between players.

In short, innovation is a subjective notion, a polymorphous concept that shapes itself according to contexts, objectives and organizational structures to deliver added value, whether economic, social or strategic.

1.2. The link between incremental and disruptive innovation

1.2.1. Conceptual clarification: Distinction between Radical Innovation and Disruptive Innovation

Radical innovation and disruptive innovation are two concepts that are often perceived as similar because of their ability to transform markets and organizations. However, while they share a significant potential for change, they differ fundamentally in their approach and impact. Radical innovation involves the introduction of entirely new technologies or products (Zahlan & al. 2023), often designed to meet unmet needs or offer functionality never before explored. This type of innovation tends to be technologically advanced and resource-intensive, but is often aimed at existing markets with a view to significantly improving current standards (Christensen 1997, Garcia & al. 2002).

Conversely, disruptive innovation targets neglected or emerging market segments with simpler, more accessible solutions, although it doesn't necessarily involve advanced new technologies (Chen & Chen, 2023). It often starts by serving customers with modest needs, before disrupting the mainstream market and challenging the dominant players (Ancillai & al. 2023). Thus, while radical innovation seeks above all to push back technological frontiers, disruptive innovation transforms the very structure of the market by changing consumer expectations and behaviors (Christensen et al., 2015; Markides, 2006). These distinctions show that while the two types of innovation can coexist, they respond to different strategies and objectives for companies.

1.2.2. Overview of recent Studies on Incremental and Disruptive Innovation

Many studies have shown that incremental and radical innovation are closely linked dynamics that, far from opposing each other, complement each other within organizations. Analysis of these forms of innovation shows that they meet distinct but interconnected objectives, ensuring both continuity and transformation in line with companies' strategic requirements (Siregar & al. 2023).

Research underlines that a strong innovation capability can integrate both incremental and radical processes to maximize impact on organizational performance (Yusof et al., 2023). By combining the complementary effects of the two forms of innovation, companies strengthen

their resilience and competitive advantage in dynamic and uncertain environments. Indeed, as Bulut et al (2022) point out, the intensity and quality of knowledge sharing play a key role in moderating the effects of radical and incremental creativity on product and process innovation, demonstrating that each type of creativity makes a distinct but compatible contribution to the development of new capabilities (Cannavacciuolo & al. 2023).

The integration of Industry 4.0 technologies, meanwhile, supports the role of incremental innovation as a key mediator in building operational and supply chain resilience (Nakandala et al., 2023). However, this incremental innovation does not supplant the need for radical innovation to ensure the profound transformations required in disruptive contexts (Harsanto & al. 2023), as radical innovation without the capacity for incremental deployment risks failing to respond to operational realities (Hervas-Oliver & al., 2022).

The role of organizational culture and leadership also appears fundamental in navigating between incremental and radical innovation. Gui & al (2022) show that transformational leadership encourages the sharing of knowledge in specific directions which, depending on their orientation (gathering or giving), favor either incremental or radical innovation. This approach is amplified by a knowledge-driven organizational culture, which guides the adoption of innovations tailored to the company's capabilities (Le & Le, 2022).

The combination of these innovations is thus a response to market turbulence, as they enable companies to strengthen their ability to adapt while preparing strategic breakthroughs for the long term (Al-Khatib & Al-ghanem, 2022). This complementarity is even more marked in technology-intensive contexts, where radical innovation enables the creation of new markets or products, while incremental innovation optimizes and adapts these creations to consolidate the company in the face of market fluctuations.

In short, incremental and radical innovation, far from being mutually exclusive, are mutually enriching. Companies that successfully combine these two forms of innovation can maximize their potential for transformation, while ensuring ongoing resilience in the face of market pressures.

1.3. Synergy between Incremental Innovation and Technological Radicality in the Moroccan Textile Industry: Towards Sustainable Competitiveness

In the context of Morocco's textile industry, the interplay between incremental and radical innovation takes on a strategic dimension, particularly in the face of the challenges of international competitiveness and sustainability. The textile industry, which is essential to the

Moroccan economy, is subject to increasing external pressures, notably due to technological developments and sustainability requirements (Yusof et al., 2023). In this industry, incremental and radical innovation can be mobilized jointly to meet these challenges, adopting continuous improvements to optimize costs and quality, while deploying disruptive technologies to access new markets or transform manufacturing processes.

Moroccan textile companies can, for example, use incremental innovation to gradually integrate sustainability practices, such as the circular economy or waste reduction (Nakandala et al., 2023). These incremental innovations respond to growing demands for environmental responsibility and enable companies to maintain their competitiveness in international supply chains, particularly in demanding markets such as Europe. At the same time, the adoption of radical innovations, such as the integration of 4.0 manufacturing technologies or new eco-responsible materials, can position Moroccan companies as pioneers in high-value-added segments, fostering a move upmarket (Al-Khatib & Al-ghanem, 2022).

Transformational leadership and knowledge sharing, highlighted by Gui, Lei, and Le (2022), are also essential to accompany these transformations in the Moroccan textile sector. A knowledge-driven innovation culture could encourage companies to combine incremental and radical innovation, ensuring rapid adaptability to market trends while preparing for the technological breakthroughs needed for the future (Zhu & al. 2023). Furthermore, in a textile sector facing high volatility in international demand, a visionary leadership approach and active support for knowledge sharing could strengthen companies' innovation and resilience capabilities (Le & Le, 2022).

1.4. Justification for our research

From the literature review, it appears that incremental and disruptive innovation play essential complementary roles, particularly in highly competitive sectors such as textiles. Indeed, several studies show that incremental innovation, through its gradual adjustments, helps maintain competitiveness and optimize processes by adapting to market requirements (Yusof & al 2023, Nakandala & al. 2023). In parallel, disruptive innovation offers a unique opportunity for technological disruption, enabling companies to redefine their positioning in the value chain by introducing new production practices or technologies (Al-Khatib & Al-ghanem, 2022).

Choosing the Moroccan textile sector for our field study is justified by its strategic importance to the Moroccan economy and its vulnerability to fluctuations in global demand, sustainability

pressures and technological transformations. Research focused specifically on incremental and disruptive innovation in this sector enables us to understand how these two types of innovation coexist and complement each other, rather than opposing them by comparing them to radical innovation. Indeed, rather than considering incremental and disruptive innovation as exclusive choices, our study examines how their combination can meet the specific needs of the Moroccan textile industry, reinforcing both its short-term adaptability and its long-term capacity for disruption. Given that innovation is contextualized according to performance criteria, this has enabled us to take into account certain performance criteria related to the textile sector.

This study builds on several theoretical frameworks to analyze the impact of incremental and disruptive innovations. The theory of disruptive innovation (Christensen, 1997; Christensen et al., 2015) provides a foundation for understanding how innovations redefine markets and challenge traditional business models. The dynamic capabilities theory (Teece, Pisano, & Shuen, 1997) highlights the need for companies to adapt their resources to effectively implement these innovations. Furthermore, studies like those of Schilling (2005) and Hervás-Oliver et al. (2022) emphasize the complementary nature of incremental and disruptive innovation in achieving both operational stability and long-term transformation. By leveraging these frameworks, this research examines how Moroccan textile companies adapt these innovation types to enhance their performance based on company size and resource allocation.

2. METHODOLOGY

To provide a rigorous answer to the question « Which innovation, between disruptive and incremental innovations, is most effective in improving the performance of industrial companies? », we had to adopt a **quantitative** approach (Creswell & al, 2018). This method makes it possible to determine precise, measurable relationships between types of innovation and company performance indicators (**productivity, cost reduction, product quality, production flexibility**), providing objectively comparable results (Simoh & al. 2022).

2.1. The field of study

The Casablanca-Settat region was chosen for this study because of its central and strategic role in the Moroccan economy. As the country's main industrial hub, the region is concentrating a wide range of companies, from small and medium-sized enterprises to large-scale industries. Casablanca-Settat is also renowned for its economic dynamism, its

concentration of infrastructure, and its access to major transport networks, making it an environment conducive to innovation (Ministère de l'Industrie et du Commerce, 2024). Studying the impact of innovations in this region thus offers a relevant and representative overview of innovation practices in Morocco's industrial sector. Moreover, companies in this region are often pioneers in adopting new technologies, making it an ideal ground for examining the effectiveness of incremental and disruptive innovations on industrial performance.

2.2. The sample selection

To select the sample for this study, we consulted specialized directories containing detailed databases with contact information for companies located in the Casablanca-Settat region. This region, both diversified and economically dynamic, is home to a large number of industrial companies, facilitating the collection of a relevant sample. Based on these databases (directories, etc.), we estimated the parent population at around **360** industrial companies, enabling us to define an optimal sample size for obtaining statistically robust results. We therefore focused on a number of 360 as the parent population, and continued our sample calculation based on this number.

To ensure optimum precision in our results, we calculated the required sample size using a margin of error of 5% and a confidence level of 95%, which resulted in an optimal size of 187 companies. This probabilistic approach was adopted to ensure the representativeness of the sample and to minimize the uncertainty of the estimates, while allowing generalization to the industrial population of the region studied.

To achieve this sample size, we initially targeted 200 business leaders, combining face-to-face and e-mail surveys to maximize the response rate. Ultimately, 174 managers responded to the questionnaire, providing a response rate sufficient to maintain the statistical rigor of the study. This representative sample enables us to draw reliable and valuable conclusions on the impact of innovations in companies in the Casablanca-Settat region. The study was conducted over a three-month period, during which the data were analyzed using Excel software.

2.3. The analysis method

To analyze the impact of incremental and disruptive innovations on the performance of industrial companies as a function of their size, we used a segmented correlations methodology. First, we segmented the data by company size (less than 50 employees, 50-250 employees, and more than 250 employees) to examine the specific effects of innovations in

distinct resource and organizational capability contexts. For each segment, we calculated correlation matrices between innovation types and different performance indicators (productivity, cost reduction, product quality, production flexibility) using Pearson correlation, which measures the strength and direction of linear relationships between two variables. The results obtained were summarized in tables for each company size, then grouped in an overall table to facilitate comparison of effects. This approach enabled us to highlight trends specific to each type of company and to formulate strategic recommendations based on the adaptability and resources specific to each size category.

3. RESULTS PRESENTATION

This section details the results obtained from the quantitative analysis carried out on the impact of incremental and disruptive innovations in the textile industrial sector, categorized by company size (Table N°1).

Table N°1: Segmented correlation results

Performance indicator	< 50 employees - Incremental Innovation	< 50 employees - Disruptive Innovation	50-250 employees - Incremental Innovation	50-250 employees - Disruptive Innovation	> 250 employees - Incremental Innovation	> 250 employees - Disruptive Innovation
Productivity	(+0.28)	0	(+0.05)	(+0.03)	(-0.07)	(+0.15)
Reduced production costs	(-0.29)	(+0.43)	(-0.01)	(+0.09)	(-0.01)	(+0.14)
Product quality	(+0.45)	(-0,05)	(-0.06)	(+0.05)	(-0.18)	(+0.29)
Production flexibility	(+0.32)	(+0.59)	(+0.05)	(-0.21)	(-0.22)	(+0.05)

Source: Authors

3.1. For companies with less than 50 employees

The figure below provides a visual illustration of the trends observed, allowing comparative analysis of the data and facilitating interpretation of the results (Figure N°1).

Figure N°1: Correlations for small enterprises

Source: Authors

The results show that, for small businesses, incremental and disruptive innovations have distinct impacts on different performance indicators. In terms of productivity, incremental innovations show a weak but positive correlation with production flexibility (+0.28), while disruptive innovations have virtually no correlation with productivity, suggesting that they do not significantly improve this indicator. This finding aligns with Yusof et al. (2023), who noted that incremental innovations often provide stability and gradual improvements in resource-constrained environments, which are characteristic of small businesses. However, the absence of a significant correlation between disruptive innovations and productivity could be due to the limited capacity of small companies to effectively absorb and implement disruptive changes, a challenge highlighted by Nakandala et al. (2023).

Regarding cost reduction, disruptive innovations show a moderately positive correlation (+0.43), while incremental innovations exhibit a negative correlation (-0.29). This supports the argument by Christensen et al. (2015) that disruptive innovations, even in small-scale operations, can streamline processes and reduce costs more effectively than incremental approaches. However, the negative impact of incremental innovations on cost reduction might stem from the initial costs associated with gradual improvements, as noted by Hervas-Oliver et al. (2022).

In terms of product quality, incremental innovations demonstrate a moderately positive correlation (+0.45), whereas disruptive innovations show weak or negative correlations (-

0.47). This divergence is consistent with Al-Khatib and Al-ghanem (2022), who suggested that disruptive innovations often require significant adaptation efforts, which may initially compromise product quality in resource-limited settings. Incremental innovations, on the other hand, allow for smoother enhancements in quality without major disruptions.

Finally, for production flexibility, both types of innovations show positive correlations, with disruptive innovations demonstrating a stronger impact (+0.59) compared to incremental innovations (+0.32). This confirms findings by Gui et al. (2022), who emphasized the role of disruptive innovations in fostering operational adaptability, particularly when small businesses adopt simplified forms of these innovations.

3.2. For medium-sized companies (50-250 employees)

The figure below provides a visual illustration of the trends observed, allowing comparative analysis of the data and facilitating interpretation of the results (Figure N°2).

Source : Authors

The results show very weak correlations between innovation types and the various performance indicators. Incremental innovations have a minimal positive impact on productivity (+0.05), while disruptive innovations show a similarly weak positive effect. This finding partially supports the work of Dupuis and Masingue (2023), who argued that medium-

sized companies may struggle to achieve significant productivity gains from either innovation type due to limited scalability.

For cost reduction, disruptive innovations exhibit a weak positive correlation (+0.09), while incremental innovations show a negligible effect (-0.01). These results are consistent with Schilling (2005), who noted that the cost advantages of disruptive innovations are more pronounced in environments capable of accommodating change, which medium-sized companies may only partially achieve.

Regarding product quality, disruptive innovations have a slight positive correlation (+0.05), contrasting with a weak negative correlation for incremental innovations (-0.06). This difference could reflect the capacity of medium-sized companies to experiment with disruptive changes, albeit cautiously, as observed by Le and Le (2022).

Finally, for production flexibility, incremental innovations show a limited positive impact (+0.05), while disruptive innovations demonstrate a slightly negative correlation (-0.21). This aligns with the findings of Nakandala et al. (2023), suggesting that disruptive changes may introduce complexity that temporarily hinders flexibility in medium-sized enterprises.

3.3. For large-sized companies (More than 250 employees)

The figure below provides a visual illustration of the trends observed, allowing comparative analysis of the data and facilitating interpretation of the results (Figure N°3).

Source : Authors

The results reveal varied trends for large companies. Incremental innovations show a negligible or negative correlation with most performance indicators, particularly flexibility (-0.22) and product quality (-0.18). These findings resonate with Hervas-Oliver et al. (2022), who noted that incremental improvements in rigid, large-scale systems often yield diminishing returns. Conversely, disruptive innovations demonstrate more favorable effects, particularly on product quality (+0.29) and cost reduction (+0.14), confirming conclusions by Christensen et al. (2015) regarding the transformative potential of disruptive innovations in resource-rich environments.

The weak but positive correlation between disruptive innovations and productivity (+0.15) also aligns with the findings of Bulut et al. (2022), who emphasized the role of well-structured processes and resources in maximizing the benefits of radical changes in large organizations. However, the minimal impact of disruptive innovations on production flexibility (+0.05) highlights the challenges large companies face in adapting their operations to significant disruptions, as noted by Gui et al. (2022).

4. DISCUSSION

4.1. Incremental innovation and company size

For small companies, incremental innovations show a moderately positive correlation with product quality and a slight positive correlation with production flexibility. This trend is understandable, given that small businesses, often limited in resources, prefer to adopt incremental changes. Incremental improvements enable them to optimize processes without excessive costs and risks. This incremental strategy provides them with the stability they need to ensure product quality without major disruption to operations. The negative correlation between incremental innovations and cost reduction for this category could indicate that small businesses do not achieve immediate cost gains through these gradual improvements. Costs related to resources or production equipment remain unchanged, and incremental improvements may require small investments without direct cost reductions.

In medium-sized companies, the weak or almost non-existent correlations between incremental innovations and performance indicators show that this strategy of gradual change produces limited benefits. This trend can be explained by the fact that, for medium-sized companies, the minor adjustments brought about by incremental innovations are often not profound enough to generate significant gains in productivity, flexibility or cost reduction. Slightly negative for product quality, this correlation could also indicate that too moderate an

approach to innovation fails to meet the demands of competitiveness in a fast-changing environment. Medium-sized companies, while retaining the flexibility of their structures, may require a more ambitious adoption of innovations to achieve quality gains.

Large companies show generally negative correlations between incremental innovations and most performance indicators, notably flexibility and product quality. This result may reflect the fact that incremental improvements in large structures, which often have complex and highly integrated production processes, can limit significant gains. Incremental adjustments, while effective for smaller structures, are likely to generate high implementation costs and low performance gains in larger companies. These companies may also be hampered by more rigid organizational structures, making the impact of incremental innovations on flexibility and cost reduction more limited.

4.2. Disruptive innovation and company size

Small businesses show a moderately positive correlation between disruptive innovations and cost reduction and production flexibility. This may be explained by the fact that disruptive innovations enable them to adopt new technologies or methods that simplify processes and reduce operational costs. By contrast, the impact of disruptive innovations on product quality is more variable, with weak or even negative correlations. This trend can be interpreted by the fact that small businesses, while they may benefit from new technologies, may also face challenges in terms of their ability to manage major transformations. The lack of resources to absorb and master the impact of these innovations on quality can indeed limit qualitative gains.

Medium-sized companies show weak but positive correlations between disruptive innovations and indicators such as productivity and cost reduction. Although these benefits are moderate, they indicate that disruptive innovations are beginning to play a role in the competitiveness of medium-sized companies, without disrupting their organization. This corresponds to the ability of medium-sized companies to absorb change without excessive rigidity and to use disruptive innovations to create small but significant competitive advantages. However, a slightly negative correlation with production flexibility is visible, which may mean that disruptive innovations, by introducing deeper changes in operations, can create additional complexity for medium-sized companies, resulting in a loss of short-term flexibility. It is also possible that the intermediate structures and resources of medium-sized companies limit their ability to adapt quickly to radical changes.

Large companies show moderately positive correlations between disruptive innovations and key indicators such as product quality and, to a lesser extent, cost reduction. These results are consistent with the idea that large companies often possess well-defined resources, skills and processes to adopt and integrate disruptive innovations, especially when they are geared towards quality improvement. They can, in fact, bear the initial risks and costs associated with adopting radical technologies, and reap lasting benefits, particularly in terms of production quality. The weak or non-existent correlations observed for production flexibility show that large companies, despite their resources, do not necessarily gain in agility with disruptive innovations. This result is logical, as the adoption of these innovations requires profound adjustments in already rigid structures, and the transformation of operations may require time and significant organizational effort.

CONCLUSION

To sum up, it was revealed that company size has a decisive influence on the choice and impact of innovations adopted, as well as the performance criterion. Smaller companies mainly benefit from incremental innovations, which promote quality and flexibility without disrupting their limited resources, while disruptive innovations offer them gains in cost and flexibility, although their impact on quality needs to be monitored. Medium-sized companies benefit from disruptive innovations in terms of productivity and cost reduction, although this can lead to rigidity requiring accompanying strategies. Large companies, on the other hand, benefit greatly from disruptive innovations, especially in terms of quality and costs, although they may encounter challenges in terms of flexibility.

From a scientific perspective, this research contributes to the existing literature by providing empirical evidence on the differentiated impacts of incremental and disruptive innovations across various company sizes in the textile sector. It highlights the contextual nature of innovation strategies, emphasizing the need to consider organizational characteristics, such as size and resources, when designing innovation policies. Furthermore, this study enriches the theoretical framework by demonstrating how the interplay between innovation types and performance indicators can guide the formulation of more effective industrial strategies. These findings offer a foundation for future research to explore similar dynamics in other sectors or geographic contexts, as well as to examine the long-term effects of innovation adoption.

This research has certain limitations that could be addressed in future studies. Firstly, the analysis focused exclusively on the textile industrial sector in the Casablanca-Settat region, limiting the generalizability of the results to other sectors and regions. In addition, the data were treated in a cross-sectional manner, without taking into account the long-term effects of innovations, which could reveal interesting evolutionary dynamics. Furthermore, this study did not explore contextual factors, such as institutional support and cultural characteristics, which can influence the impact of innovations. Future research could extend this framework by incorporating longitudinal analyses to observe how the impact of innovations evolves over time, as well as examining other sectors for a better comparison of effects.

ANNEX

The questionnaire translated into English :

Industry (Choose one option only) :

- Clothing and apparel
- Fabrics and technical textiles
- Leather and leather products
- Fashion accessories (bags, belts, etc.)

Company size :

- Less than 50 employees
- 50-250 employees
- More than 250 employees

For each type of innovation, indicate the frequency of adoption in your company. (Note that this question generates numerical data, facilitating correlation analysis).

How often do you adopt incremental innovations?

- 1 = Never
- 2 = Once a year
- 3 = Several times a year
- 4 = Very frequently (every quarter)

How often do you adopt disruptive innovations?

- 1 = Never
- 2 = Every 3-5 years
- 3 = Every 1-2 years
- 4 = Every year

For each performance indicator below, rate the impact of incremental and disruptive innovations using a scale from 1 to 5, where:

- 1 = No impact**
- 5 = Very significant impact**

A. Productivity

Incremental innovation: [1] [2] [3] [4] [5]
Disruptive innovation: [1] [2] [3] [4] [5]

B. Reducing production costs

Incremental innovation: [1] [2] [3] [4] [5]
Disruptive innovation: [1] [2] [3] [4] [5]

C. Improving product quality

Incremental innovation: [1] [2] [3] [4] [5]
Disruptive innovation: [1] [2] [3] [4] [5]

D. Production flexibility

Incremental innovation: [1] [2] [3] [4] [5]
Disruptive innovation: [1] [2] [3] [4] [5]

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Aharouay, S., & Rajaa, M. (2023). La gouvernance d'entreprise : une variable pertinente d'innovation organisationnelle. *Moroccan Journal of Entrepreneurship, Innovation and Management (MJEIM)*, 4(2), 32-42.
2. Al-Khatib, A.W., & Al-ghanem, E.M. (2022). Radical innovation, incremental innovation, and competitive advantage, the moderating role of technological intensity: Evidence from the manufacturing sector in Jordan. *European Business Review*, 34(3), 344-369.
3. Ancillai, C., Sabatini, A., Gatti, M., & Perna, A. (2023). Digital technology and business model innovation: A systematic literature review and future research agenda. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 188, 122307.
4. Azmat, F., Lim, W. M., Moyeen, A., Voola, R., & Gupta, G. (2023). Convergence of business, innovation, and sustainability at the tipping point of the sustainable development goals. *Journal of Business Research*, 167, 114170.
5. Bahoo, S., Cucculelli, M., & Qamar, D. (2023). Artificial intelligence and corporate innovation: A review and research agenda. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 188, 122264.
6. Bulut, C., Kaya, T., Mehta, A.M., & Danish, R.Q. (2022). Linking incremental and radical creativity to product and process innovation with organisational knowledge. *Journal of Manufacturing Technology Management*, 33(4), 763-784.
7. Cannavacciuolo, L., Ferraro, G., Ponsiglione, C., Primario, S., & Quinto, I. (2023). Technological innovation-enabling industry 4.0 paradigm: a systematic literature review. *Technovation*, 124, 102733.
8. Chen, S. L., & Chen, K. L. (2023). Exploring the Impact of Technological Innovation on the Development of Electric Vehicles on the Bibliometric Perspective of Innovation Types. *World Electric Vehicle Journal*, 14(7), 191.
9. Christensen, C. M. (1997). *The Innovator's Dilemma: When New Technologies Cause Great Firms to Fail*. Harvard Business Review Press.
10. Christensen, C. M., Raynor, M. E., & McDonald, R. (2015). What is disruptive innovation? *Harvard Business Review*, 93(12), 44-53.
11. Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2018). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches* (5th ed.). SAGE Publications.
12. Dupuis, J., & Masingue, A. (2023). L'innovation organisationnelle et managériale dans les intercommunalités françaises : Entre stratégie d'adaptation et stratégie d'anticipation ? *Management international*, 27(2), 66-78. <https://doi.org/10.59876/a-grms-jacc>
13. Gama, F., & Magistretti, S. (2023). Artificial intelligence in innovation management: A review of innovation capabilities and a taxonomy of AI applications. *Journal of Product Innovation Management*.
14. Garcia, R., & Calantone, R. (2002). A critical look at technological innovation typology and innovativeness terminology: A literature review. *Journal of Product Innovation Management*, 19(2), 110-132. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1540-5885.1920110>

15. Glaeser, S., & Lang, M. (2024). Measuring innovation and navigating its unique information issues: A review of the accounting literature on innovation. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 101720.
16. Gui, L., Lei, H., & Le, P.B. (2022). Determinants of radical and incremental innovation: The influence of transformational leadership, knowledge sharing and knowledge-centered culture. *European Journal of Innovation Management*, 25(5), 1221-1241.
17. Harsanto, B., Primiana, I., Sarasi, V., & Satyakti, Y. (2023). Sustainability innovation in the textile industry: a systematic review. *Sustainability*, 15(2), 1549.
18. Hervas-Oliver, J.-L., Sempere-Ripoll, F., & Moll, C. B. (2022). Zooming into firms' location, capabilities and innovation performance: Does agglomeration foster incremental or radical innovation? *European Research on Management and Business Economics*, 28, 100186.
19. LAKHLIFI, F. Z., & ABDELLAOUI, M. (2024). Évaluation théorique de l'impact de la Stratégie Industrielle 2023-2030 sur la performance du secteur industriel au Maroc. *Revue Internationale des Sciences de Gestion*, 7(4).
20. Le, P.T., & Le, P.B. (2022). Influence of knowledge-oriented leadership and knowledge sharing on radical and incremental innovation: The moderating role of market turbulence. *VINE Journal of Information and Knowledge Management Systems*.
21. Markides, C. (2006). Disruptive innovation: In need of better theory. *Journal of Product Innovation Management*, 23(1), 19-25. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-5885.2005.00177.x>
22. Ministère de l'Industrie et du Commerce. (2024). Rapport annuel sur l'Observatoire de la Politique de Développement. MIC. <https://mcinet.gov.ma/>
23. Nakandala, D., Yang, R., Lau, H., & Weerabahu, S. (2023). Industry 4.0 technology capabilities, resilience and incremental innovation in Australian manufacturing firms: A serial mediation model. *Supply Chain Management*, 28(4), 760-772.
24. OUDDA, B., & JALLAL, R. (2024). Vers une stratégie RH innovante: Une revue de littérature sur l'évolution de la place du facteur humain dans l'innovation. *Revue Française d'Economie et de Gestion*, 5(6).
25. Rhazzane, H., Ahachmi, A., & Lahfidi, A. (2023). L'impact de l'innovation organisationnelle et de l'intelligence économique sur la résilience des coopératives au Maroc. *Journal of Cooperative Studies*, 6(1), 142-157.
26. Schilling, M. A. (2005). *Strategic Management of Technological Innovation*. McGraw-Hill Education.
27. SIMOH, M., TAHAR, M. B., & FADLALLAH, A. (2022). Essai de mesure de la performance globale des entreprises: Cas des entreprises nationales du secteur du textile et d'habillement. *International Journal of Accounting, Finance, Auditing, Management and Economics*, 3(4-3), 327-345.
28. Siregar, O. M., Marpaung, N., Nasution, M. D. T. P., & Harahap, R. (2023, May). A Literature Review on Incremental Innovations in Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises: Bridging Knowledge Gaps and Future Research Avenues. In *International*

- Conference on Business and Technology (pp. 258-269). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.
29. Teece, D. J., Pisano, G., & Shuen, A. (1997). Dynamic capabilities and strategic management. *Strategic Management Journal*, 18(7), 509-533. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1097-0266\(199708\)18:7](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1097-0266(199708)18:7)
 30. Yusof, N., Kamal, E. M., Lou, E. C. W., & Kamaruddeen, A. M. (2023). Effects of innovation capability on radical and incremental innovations and business performance relationships. *Journal of Engineering and Technology Management*, 67, 101726.
 31. Zahlan, A., Ranjan, R. P., & Hayes, D. (2023). Artificial intelligence innovation in healthcare: Literature review, exploratory analysis, and future research. *Technology in society*, 102321.
 32. Zhu, Z. Y., Xie, H. M., & Chen, L. (2023). ICT industry innovation: Knowledge structure and research agenda. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 189, 122361.